

SENTIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF RESTAURANT REVIEWS USING MACHINE LEARNING

Jans Alphonsa Jacob
Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala, India
Jansalphonsajacob68@gmail.com

Amal K Jose
Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala, India
amalkjose@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Sentiment analysis is one method for categorizing articles to identify positively or negatively opinions. Customer service's most important component is client contentment. A restaurant is a business that needs to pay greater attention to providing clients with better service over time. This study uses Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, and SVM to categorise restaurant customer delight. According to the research's findings, these three methods are successful at capturing the customer's response. Sentiment analysis using the logistic regression method is 0.28 percent more accurate.

Keywords:- Sentiment Analysis, Decision tree, Support Vector Machine, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sentiment analysis is a crucial component of customer happiness, or the sense that exists between a client's expectations and reality. These days, a lot of users post reviews of their thoughts on social networking sites like Twitter. Online customer reviews are crucial because they could boost the seller's goods or service's popularity. For instance, the first step in using a service or staying at a restaurant is to go online and read customer reviews of that establishment. Reviewing a business, services, or other entities is a process. User comments on any product, including books, are completely free to submit. Even a collection of reviews might be considered a review.

A user review is an evaluation that is written by a user for a specific product or service based on that person's experience with the subject matter of the review. The sentiment analysis is employed to comprehend the writer's emotional intent behind their text. Based on their writing, it determines whether a person has a good, negative, or neutral attitude. Consumer behaviour research and marketing are both heavily focused on customer satisfaction. When customers experience outstanding service, they will tell others about it, just like with hotel guests. Using analytical tools or manuals, text mining is the

process of retrieving data from a group of frequently stored documents. Information that can be utilised to improve sales and services may be created by studying various text mining perspectives. Customer reviews are still in text form on TripAdvisor, and restaurant reviews fall under the text mining area. The outcomes of these data will be categorised into two values: positive or negative. Commerce sites like Amazon.com, TripAdvisor, and other well-known ones are some of the sites where we may see customer reviews. The consistency with which sentences' sentiments are expressed in restaurant reviews. Data from restaurants can be subjected to sentiment analysis, which will categorise each message as either good or negative.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Nasa Zata Dina et.al. [1] The study offers information to both the employer and the job seeker. The job seeker may be able to choose the organisation that best meets his needs and abilities with the aid of the review analysis. Companies will be better aware of their strengths and limitations, which may be a big help to them. Based on the identified factors, this study might also assign rankings to the businesses.

Parandham et.al. [2] The method of sentiment analysis is being tested by researchers in the fields of natural language processing (NLP), data mining, machine learning, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and sentiment analysis.

Masrur Adnan et.al. [3] The Decision Tree-J48 method's total performance is represented by an average of Precision 48.7%, Recall 36.8%, F-Measure 41.40%, and correctness 45.6%. The advantage of these classification findings is that they serve as a suggestion for customers to select the best restaurant.

Pooja Tyagi et.al. [4] User evaluations and electronic word-of-mouth have a significant influence on decision-making. A company or organisation can learn what they are greatest and worst at using this analysis. That will aid in resolving worst-case scenarios for the relevant aspects.

Spoorthi C et.al. [5] By applying data mining techniques and the r tool, the problem with text data can be overcome. For the effective prediction of text data, our experimental effort will use data mining approaches such as the Naive Bayes classifier. The reviews in this data set are real ones from real people. As a result, this data collection will provide real-world expertise with handling textual data.

Levels of Sentiment Analysis:

Sentiment analysis can be utilised at many degrees of scope:

- **Document Level Sentiment Analysis:** The Sentiment Analysis module at the document level examines a passage of text and decides if it has a positive or negative sentiment. It supports all texts with emotional content.
- **Word level sentimental analysis:** Word-level contextual sentiment analysis (WCSA) is a critical activity for mining evaluations or opinions. While researching this kind of attitude in the sector, it is frequently required to take into account both the interpretability and the practicality. However, no such WCSA technique has been created.
- **Sentence level sentimental analysis:** Identifying whether each sentence reflects a good, negative, or neutral opinion is the task at this level.
- **Aspect Based Sentimental Analysis:** Aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA), a machine learning task, recognises and assigns sentiment to the aspects, features, and subjects that it has identified and annotated in the body of data

Types of sentiment analysis:

1. **Fine-Grained Sentimental Analysis:** This sentiment analysis model aids in polarity precision determination. The polarity categories of extremely positive, positive, neutral, negative, or very negative can all be used in a sentiment analysis.
2. **Aspect-Based Sentimental Analysis:** In-depth aspect-based analysis goes deeper, and fine-grained analysis helps you determine the general polarity of your customers' evaluations. It helps in pinpointing the exact characteristics being discussed.
3. **Emotion Detection Sentimental Analysis:** Emotion detection, as its name suggests, aids in emotion recognition.

These emotions include rage, grief, joy, and gratification as well as fear, concern, and panic. Lexicons, or collections of words that express particular emotions, are frequently used by emotion detection systems.

4. **Intent Analysis Sentimental Analysis:** Companies may save time, money, and effort by correctly identifying consumer intent. This problem can be solved through accurate intent analysis. The intent analysis aids in determining whether a buyer is intending to make a purchase or is merely looking around.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

1. Obtaining data for training and testing ML classifiers
2. Processing data
3. Fitting and training the model

A. DATA DESCRIPTION:

The dataset, which was derived from Kaggle and is divided into five pieces, gives us business information. The training dataset's csv file contains the fields id, review, and liked.

B. PREPROCESSING:

The text must be cleaned before being fed into any model as part of NLP, which is essentially sentiment analysis. The preprocessed data collection, which is utilised for training and testing, accomplishes this. Cleaning typically involves deleting punctuation and turning all text to lower case. Removing stop words like "a," "an," and that aren't important for determining mood. Likewise, The Bag of Words In order to generate the model using sentiment analysis, it is essential to create a sparse matrix with distinct terms from each review as its columns and each row representing a review. The bag-of-words (BOW) model counts the occurrences of each word in any text to convert it into fixed-length vectors. Any text is transformed into fixed-length vectors via the (BOW) model.

C. MODEL FITTING AND TRAINING

1. Logistic Regression:

Using prior observations from a data set, a statistical analysis technique called logistic regression predicts a binary outcome, such as yes or no.

2. Naive Bayes:

A classification algorithm that works well for binary and multiclass classification is called Naive Bayes. Compared to numerical input variables, naive Bayes performs better in cases of categorical input variables. It is helpful for forecasting data and making predictions based on past outcomes.

3. Support Vector Machine:

Classification and regression issues are resolved using Support Vector Machine, one of the most used supervised learning techniques. It is mostly used, nevertheless, in Machine Learning Classification problems

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To demonstrate the findings of the experiment, this section compares the classification accuracy of three machine learning approaches to sentiment analysis. The logistic regression's accuracy is 0.82%. Naive Bayes has an accuracy rate of 0.73%. The SVM's accuracy is 0.81%. The highest accuracy is 0.82 percent.

a) Logistic Regression

b) Naive Bayes

c) Support Vector Machine

V. CONCLUSION

This research presents an analysis of important techniques for determining sentiment analysis of reviews. In this study, the primary techniques for determining the sentiment analysis of the review text under examination are described. We compare all accessible approaches, employ Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, and SVM to the fullest extent possible. By classifying the reviews as positive or negative, the Logistic Regression approach is efficiently employed to determine the polarity of the reviews in this case.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Nasa Zata Dina, Nyoman Juniarta "Aspect based Sentiment Analysis of Employee's Review Experience", Journal of Information Systems Engineering and Business Intelligence, 2020
- [2] Parandham, Mr. Raghavendra "Sentiment Analysis of Restaurant Reviews", International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science (IRJMET), 2021
- [3] Masrur Adnan, Riyanarto Sarno, Kelly Rossa Sungkono "Sentiment Analysis of Restaurant Review with Classification Approach in the Decision Tree-J48 Algorithm", Internal Seminar on Application for Technology, 2019
- [4] Pooja Tyagi "Sentiment Analysis of Restaurant Reviews", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IJERT), 2020
- [5] Spoorthi C, Dr. Pushpa Ravi Kumar, Mr. Adarsh M. J. "International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IJERT)", 2020